

Persistent Excitation

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Abstract: A personal reflection on the occasion of Prof. Nina Thornhill's retirement.

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1. Who is N.F.Thornhill?

One of the most exciting experiences for a young PhD student is to grow a network of academic contacts and to get to know other researchers. This mostly happens through reading other people's publications.

As a PhD student this means your impression of a person is built only by means of a written publication. This is probably the most neutral entrance into other people's work.

One of my most remarkable such experiences as a PhD student at the Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm, was by reading the paper on performance assessment and diagnosis of refinery control loops (Thornhill et al., 1998).

The paper was practical, useful, well written, as many others. And it gave me my first great learning. My PhD topic was on control loop monitoring, i.e. finding out whether a control loop is properly tuned when only routine measurement data is available and hardly any other information.

Nina also worked on this – still today – important practical problem¹ together with some people from the refining industry. At that time, most people in the loop monitoring community started their research with Thomas Harris' seminal paper that used minimum-variance control to benchmark current control loop performance (Harris, 1989).

One drawback of that method was the fact that the apparent or real process time-delay needed to be known. Minimum-variance control achieves the best possible control w.r.t. to the process delay which fundamentally limits the achievable control performance.

¹ In general, I have the impression that the amount of mis-tuned basic control loops in the process industry still is by far too large. Today one may calculate the huge amount of CO₂ that is produced unnecessarily due to this.

The idea that Nina's paper proposed took my breath: instead of trying to find out what a control loop's real time delay was, their paper proposed to rather use it as a design variable! What a wonderful idea to turn weakness into strength and create new possibilities.

It is this kind of lateral thinking that open up a PhD student's thinking and enriched my own work considerably. Pursuing an engineering PhD is less about doing the math (also that), but much more learning to understand real-world problems and finding new ways to solve them. This was my first such experience which still follows me here and there: think outside the box!

Not only Nina's work followed me through my PhD studies. I finally met her and one of her PhD students a few years later. Margret Bauer worked as PhD student with transfer entropy to analyse disturbances propagating through a process plant.

Later, I had the pleasure to use Margret's algorithms on some of my PhD project's data. It nicely confirmed both Margret's results as well as one of my own algorithms.

This was my second experience with Nina during my PhD studies: The approach of using transfer entropy (Kantz & Schreiber, 1997) for disturbance analysis came from a completely different field of science! In hindsight, this may not sound very spectacular, but it threw me out of my engineering bubble at that time.

What impressed me during that period of collaboration with Nina and Margret (and later also when studying Ines Cecilio's PhD thesis for her viva) is the comprehensive approach to PhD studies. Nina's PhD students start with a clear research question and a solid curriculum is then built around that research question. The scientific work always tackled that question with a 360° approach. Something that also became apparent when reading Nina's scientific papers.

It was therefore natural that my PhD supervisor Alf Isaksson invited Nina for my PhD defence. In Sweden the PhD defence requires a committee of four people. As the main opponent Thomas Harris from Queen's University Ontario was kind enough to act and the committee consisted of Nina Thornhill, Morten Hovd (NTNU, Norway) and Tore Hägglund (LTH, Sweden).

I am still honoured and happy that I had the possibility to defend my academic work in front of such a top-class committee!

3. ABB Professorship

After my PhD I started to work for ABB Corporate Research in Germany. I stayed in the area of performance and process monitoring, so it was natural to keep in touch with Nina at University College London and later at Imperial College when Nina moved there as the ABB/Royal Academy of Engineering professor of Process Automation.

ABB was wise enough to fund an ABB professorship at Imperial College London, strongly supported by ABB's CTO at the time, Peter Terwiesch.

Nina's collaboration with ABB started with her support of our efforts to productise both control loop monitoring algorithms and plant-wide disturbance analysis software.

In a very fruitful collaboration with the colleagues from the ABB Research Center in Norway we implemented algorithms stemming from Nina's own research and Margret's PhD thesis. Nina was much involved in this work. What I valued very much at that time was her serious attitude when it came to finding solutions for (real-world) technical problems.

Her humble attitude made everyone round the table feel valued and invited. I have seldom experienced someone so open, interested, taking all people seriously and talking to them at eye-level, always. Having been involved in many academic – industrial projects, I have to admit, that such an enjoyable collaboration is rare.

Not only was the work pleasant, we also used the resulting software tool to analyse some real-world problems where

propagating disturbances in a process plant were analysed to find the underlying root cause.

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I had the pleasure to visit John Cox at Eastman Chemical Company in the U.S. We applied the new algorithms to some data exhibiting clear plant-wide disturbances and they picked the (known) root-causes in each of the cases perfectly!

This was something that shaped my academic philosophy. If someone works on a scientific solution of practical industrial problems, there are three aspects that have to be considered:

1. Algorithms need to be simple to apply; otherwise they will never be used.
2. Algorithms need to work properly. Their tuning has to be simple or automatic; otherwise they will never be used.
3. Algorithms must be developed doing the science right. Ad-hoc solutions will fail one or the other way.

All this is true for the work that I was fortunate enough to learn from Nina and her co-workers. It gave me a good start into my industrial career at ABB.

Today, I am working with programmable logic controllers for functional safety in oil, gas and rail applications. The learnings from my PhD time, many of them triggered from Nina still help me to do my work successfully.

One of my most cited publications also stems from the ABB collaboration with Nina while she was at Imperial College. In 2007, I was very happy to co-author the paper (Thornhill & Horch, 2007) where we collected a survey of work about plant-wide disturbance analysis.

Even though for me working in industry, citation indices do not matter, I am happy to see that this paper is the No. 3 of my own ranking with around 200 citations.

More importantly, the important work around plant-wide disturbance analysis has initiated numerous research groups worldwide to start working in this area. Today, there are countless papers written on this topic. This probably is the best reward someone can get: initiate other research group to extend one's own work and research question.

I am not aware that this has led to a large-scale implementation in industry so far. It would be beneficial for companies to apply tools for plant-wide disturbance analysis because plant upsets and in extreme cases also shutdowns, must be avoided. At the very least, waste of energy, production or too high CO₂ emissions could be avoided by running plants more smoothly. This mandate comes with new urgency in 2019 where the climate crisis echoes too little in industry in my opinion. Energy efficiency has to be put on the agenda again with new impetus.

These tools, however, will hardly run autonomously, they need expertise, at least in order to analyse the results. The trend in the process industry, however is the opposite: cost saving programs reduce the amount of skilled engineers in the plants. And their daily duties often overwhelm them such that this kind of plant optimization has no space.

Another collaboration should be mentioned, which illustrates Nina's dedication to good work. In ABB we worked on combining plant-wide disturbance data analysis with topology-information available from plants. At that time, 2005, the term Industrie 4.0 was still 6 years from seeing the light of day, using electronic information together with measurement data was still unusual and often difficult.

To overcome this problem, Nina sent two of her top students to Germany to work on that problem. Sok Yee and Harri Govind delivered tremendous results based on LISP and automatic processing of plant topology information that was available in XML-format (Yim et al., 2006). For me, that was the start into the Industrie 4.0 age.

This again was a remarkable example for tackling challenging industrial problems with a holistic scientific approach. The ability to finish scientific work not only be doing the math, but also to make sure a working software proves the math is something I have largely admired.

4. Oil and Gas Industry

In 2011, I changed my career into management rather than technical R&D and I had to let closer technical collaboration with Nina go. By that time, her focus has moved into the oil and gas industry together with ABB units in Norway and Poland.

I followed her work in this area from a distance. One thing, however, was apparent: Nina's way of bringing thorough scientific approaches into industrial practice continued in the area of compressor control.

The collaboration was successful and ran very smooth. Nina spent long time in both Norway and Poland and became a great expert in compressor technology. Other people in this Festschrift will most likely describe this work in more detail.

One very remarkable outcome of the ABB collaboration was probably the industrial plant that Nina helped to build, instrument and operate at Imperial College (<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/corporate-partnerships/industrial-collaborations/abb/>). I was not involved in that project, but had the ability to visit the plant. It was overwhelming to see that an academic laboratory plant can actually look like a real-world chemical pilot plant.

For me, this plant symbolises what Nina has worked for most of her career: bringing academia and industry together for the benefit of both.

6. PERSONAL CONCLUSION

I am happy and honoured that many years of my academic as well as industrial careers were accompanied by Nina, her work, her inspiring ideas, her humble and great character, her incredibly talented and nice PhD students (one of which I had the pleasure to employ at ABB and who became one of the best friends of my whole family).

Academic work is much about meeting inspiring people. And in engineering, there are still far too few female professors internationally visible. This has to change!

As much as I wish Nina all the best for her retirement, for academia and industry, it will be a huge loss.

Thank you for everything, Nina.

REFERENCES

- Thornhill NF, Oettinger M, Fedenczuk P (1998). Performance assessment and diagnosis of refinery control loops, *3rd International Conference on Foundations of Computer-Aided Process Operations*, Publisher: AMER INST CHEMICAL ENGINEERS, Pages: 373-379, ISSN: 0065-8812.
- Thomas J. Harris (1989). "Assessment of Control Loop Performance". *Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering* 67. October 1989, pages 856-861. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjce.5450670519>.
- Kantz, H., & Schreiber, T. (1997). Nonlinear time series analysis. *Cambridge University Press*.
- Thornhill, NF, Horch, A. (2007). Advances and new directions in plant-wide disturbance detection and diagnosis. *Control Engineering Practice* 15 (10), 1196-1206.
- Yim, SY, Ananthakumar, HG, Benabbas, L, Horch, A., Drath, R., Thornhill, NF (2006). Using process topology in plant-wide control loop performance assessment. *Computers & Chemical Engineering* 31 (2), 86-99.